

Reconciling The Dilemma Posed by Third-Party's Information on Revocation of An Offer on The Offeror and Offeree Under the Nigerian Contract Law

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ABSTRACT: Contract as a branch of law that consists of obligations that are self-imposed, a party cannot be held liable unless he violates the terms, he agreed to bind him. In fact, for a contract to exist, there must be a party making a proposal and if such proposition is accepted, give rise to a binding contract. However, there are some situations where this proposition can be retracted by the person making it. This demonstrates these rights and freedoms that are inherent in contractual agreements, hence, a person making an offer may wish at a point to withdraw the offer; besides, this would be unfair if the offeror having made an offer was bound to wait for an indefinite period of time before the offer was accepted. Particularly, in business arrangements, the offeror must have the opportunity to move on and find another person in order to sell his goods or services. To this end, it is possible to withdraw or revoke an offer if certain requirements are met. This study is set to expose these requirements and provide for justification of third party's place in revocation of offer by both parties.

KEYWORDS: Contract; Dilemma; Offeree; Offeror; Third-party; Revocation of Offer.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The law of contract is part of the law of obligations.¹ It concerns bargains that are made between parties. The major significance of the word “bargain” is that it involves agreement that is binding on the both parties.² This is why the learned Professor Sagay defined the term contract as agreement which the law will enforce or at least recognize as affecting the legal rights and of the parties.³ It is also defined as a voluntary agreement whereby a person undertakes and duties for reward (consideration) to person an act for another where the terms are contemplated and admitted by the parties.⁴ Simply, a contract is an agreement enforceable at law, the most striking issue here is that the law does create the terms or rights/duties for the parties but only recognize and enforce them.

Deducing from the foregoing, it is very clear to state that for a contract to exist there must be an agreement. Jacqueline Martin and Chris Turner quickly added that a contract is only formed in law where the following can be shown to exist: agreement, consideration and intention.⁵ This agreement is seen as mutuality of purpose mutual assent of two parties to certain terms⁶ or a consensus of two or more minds in anything done or to be done.⁷

As earlier noted, we have seen that the law of contract is about “bargain”. The major significance of the word “bargain” is that it involves an agreement that is binding on both parties. A contract is sealed and completed when both sides honour an agreement by carrying out their side of the contract. When they fail to carry out their particular sides, it becomes a breach of contract.

On what constitute the valid elements of a contract, the Supreme Court in *Oloja v. Gov., Benue State*⁸ had this to say;

In other words, for an enforceable contract to materialise between parties, there must co-exist a precise offer, an unqualified acceptance and a legal consideration with the intent to create a legal relationship. The hallmark of a valid contract is *consensus ad idem*, the meeting of minds by the parties concerned.

An intention to enter into legal relations which is the fourth element, although parties to a contract do not consciously contemplate this element when entering into a contract.⁹

¹ P.S Atiyah, *An Introduction to the Law of Contract*, 4th Ed. (Oxford, Clarendon Law Series, 2006)

² C Turner & J. Martin, *Unlocking Contract Law* 4th Ed. (London, Hodder Education, 2010)

³ I.E Sagay, *Nigeria Law of Contract*, 3rd Ed (Ibadan, Spectrum Books 2000)

⁴ *Obmami Brick and stone Nig. Ltd. V African Continental Bank* (1992) NWLR VOL.3 Pt 229 pg 260

⁵ Turner (n 2)

⁶ *Constain West African Ltd. V. Savol West African Ltd.* (2015) ALL FWRL 251 page 223

⁷ *Zahkem Constitution Ltd. V. Nneji* (2002) 5NWLR 79 page 55 also in Latin – “Consensus as idem”

⁸ (2022) 3 NWLR (Pt. 1816) 1

⁹ Indeed, Niki Tobi, J.C.A, adds a Fifth element, namely capacity to contract, in *Oriet Bank V Bilante Intl.* (1998).8 NWLR (Pt. 515) 37 at 16, but again this element is taken for granted and is thus not usually listed among primary elements

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Traditionally, in order to bring a contract into being there must be a mutual assent. The mutual assent of the parties to it must be capable of being broken down into offer and acceptance. The mutual assent is of no legal significance indeed; it will lead to intolerable confusion and uncertainty if mutual assent is tested subjectively. The test is objective and seeks to elicit the apparent intention of the parties. In the words of Lord Dunedin: "commercial contracts cannot be arranged by what people think in their innermost heads, commercial contracts are made according to what people say."¹⁰

2.0 CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

Succinctly, for a contract (an agreement) to be ensued, there must be an offer and an unqualified acceptance.¹¹ We shall consider some of the elements of bargain with emphasis on offer for a better understanding of the work.

2.1 Acceptance.

It is trite law that for an offer to amount to a contract. The terms must be accepted by the offeree. It would therefore be correct to state that to make a binding contract; the acceptance must exactly match the offer. That is, the offeree must accept all the terms of the offer. It was defined in the case of *Orient Bank Nigeria Plc. V. Bilante International Ltd.*¹² Acceptance in the law of contract is the reciprocal act or actions of the offeree to the offer in which he indicates his agreement in terms of offer.¹³

The Court in the case of *Innih V. Ferrado A & C Ltd*¹⁴ stated clearly that for an acceptance to be valid, it must be plain, unequivocal, unconditional, must not be at variance with the terms of the offer, must be communicated without unreasonable delay.

2.2 Consideration

This was defined by Sir. Fredrick Pollock as a price for which the promise of the other party is bought.¹⁵ It was also defined as the inducement to contract, it is the cause, reason, motive, price or impelling influence which induce a contracting party to enter into a contract.¹⁶

2.3 Dilemma

The word Dilemma, is from a Greek for "Double proposition".¹⁷ It was originally a technical term of logic but we use it now far anytime you have a problem with no satisfactory solution. It could also mean a state of uncertainty of perplexity especially as required choice between equally unfavourable options. For example, when you are to choose whether to save your cat or your dog from a burning building.

2.4 Third Party

A third party in any contract is one who is not a member or directly involved in a transaction between two parties.¹⁸ He is a person who is not a party to a contract but is involved with the transaction it is not directly involved the is one in whom the parties are to rely on or could rely/relied on.¹⁹

2.5 Offer

An offer according to professor Sagay is a definite undertaken or promise made by one party with the intention that it shall become binding on the other party making it as soon as the it accepted by the party to whom it is addressed.²⁰ For Chesire and Fifoot is a promise to be bound provided the terms are accepted.²¹ Professor Ademola Yakubu of blessed memory wrote that an offer is an expression of willingness or a definite undertaken to contract on certain terms by the person to whom it is made with the intention that they shall become binding as soon as it is accepted by the person to whom it is addressed.²² It is argued that the learned Professor definition is based on the decision of the court in the case of *Akanmu V. Olugbode*.²³ G.H Treitel defined an offer as an expression of willingness to contract on certain terms made with the intention that is shall become binding as soon as it is accepted by the person to whom it is addressed.²⁴

¹⁰ Muir Head and Turrbtti V Dickson (1905) IF. 686 at P 694

¹¹ Kamale V. Dahiru (2005) 9 NWLR 929 page 18.

¹² (1997)8 NWLR Pt. 515 pg 37.

¹³ Per Niki Tobi, JCA.

¹⁴ (1990) 5 NWLR pg 152

¹⁵ F. Pollock, *Pollock's Principles of Contract*, 13th Ed (London, Stevens & Sons, 1950)

¹⁶ Shell Development Company V. Allaputa (2005) 9 NWLR pt 931

¹⁷ <<https://www.vocabulary.com/dictionary/dilemma>> accessed 22nd June 2025

¹⁸ <<https://www.lawteacher.net/free-law-essays/contract-law/rights-of-third-parties-in-contract.php>> accessed 22nd June 2025

¹⁹ *Ibid*

²⁰ Sagay (n 3)

²¹ Furmston ed. Cheshire, Fifoot & Furnston, *Law of Contract*, (Butterorth, 1987)

²² J.A. Yakubu, *Law of Contract in Nigeria*, (Lagos; Malthouse, 2003)

²³ (2001) 13 WRN pay 132

²⁴ G.H. Treitel, *The Law of Contract*, 15th Ed. (Sweet & Maxwell, 1995)

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In *Abdullahi v. El-Rufai*,²⁵ the Supreme Court defines Offer as an expression of readiness to contract on the terms specified by the offeror (i.e. the person making the offer) which when it is accepted by the offeree (i.e. the person to whom the offer is made) will give rise to a valid and binding contract. Therefore, where an offer is made but is not accepted, there can be no agreement or contract arising therefrom. In other words, it is by acceptance that an offer is converted to a contract. [*Sparkling Breweries Ltd. v. U.B.N. Ltd.* (2001) 15 NWLR (Pt. 737) 539 referred to.] (P. 227, paras. B-D)

An offer must be precise and unequivocal leaving no room for speculation or conjecture as to its real content in the mind of the offeree. The offeror must place at the door steps of the offeree a clear intention and desire to enter into a contract with the offeree on clearly defined terms. The person making the offer is called offeror and the person to whom it is addressed is the offeree.²⁶ Thus, all situations involving the sale of goods and property must also involve offer and acceptance. It should be noted from the above that for there to be a contract there must be a party making an offer which must be unmistakable and precise. This was held in the case of *David Ejinyi v. Amusa Adio*²⁷ where the court held that in the absence of an offer there cannot be any acceptance giving rise to contract. The case of *Olaopa v. Obafemi Awolowo University*.²⁸ The University had some landed property in Ibadan which it wanted to put to profitable commercial use. It invited the appellant, an architect, to a meeting. The minutes of the meeting, the feasibility study and survey plan of property were sent to the appellant. On receiving this, he went ahead to draw the plan for the construction which he submitted to the university. This was followed by a bill for his fees. The University refused to pay and the appellant sued it to recover his fees. The question that arose for determination was whether there was no contact whatsoever between the parties. According to Wali, J.S.C, there was no offer capable of being converted into an agreement by acceptance as the respondent the university, had not completed its share in the formation of a contract by a final declaration of its readiness to undertake an obligation upon certain conditions which the appellant could have accepted.

We should also know that the daily routine activities performed by most human beings are contractual in nature and can be analysed into situations of offer and acceptance.²⁹ For instance, a student who goes to the market to get a measure of rice. He makes the offer and the trader accepts.

It should also be stated that there is no limit to the number of people an offer can be made to but a contract comes into existence only between the offeror and the person or the person responding to the offer and accepting it. This principle first declared in the famous case of *Carbolic Smoke Ball CO. v Carlill*.³⁰ Bowen, L.J expressly stated that an offer can be made not only to an individual or a group of persons but also to the whole world. In that case the defendants had argued that no contract could arise from their advertisement because you cannot make a contract with the whole world. This argument, the court demolished by stating as follows: It was also said that the contract is made with the whole world that is with everybody and that you cannot contract with everybody. It is not a contract made with the world. That is the fallacy of the argument. It is an offer made to all the world and why should not an offer be made all the world and why should not an offer be made to all the world which is to ripen into a contract with anybody who comes forward and performs the condition and although the offer is made to the world the contract is made to the world the contract is made to the world the contract is made with that limited portion of the public who come forward and perform the condition on the faith of the advertisement.³¹

The case establishes a unilateral contract. This is a situation where one party may simply make an offer by which he intends to be bound to any person willing to accept and perform or abide by the demands of the offer. In this case the offer is usually not made to any particular person but to the world at large or to a given class of persons and any person who is interested in the terms of the offer and who falls within the class therein mentioned may accept the same by simply performing the task demanded by the offer.

The court at sometimes, examine statements to determine what amount to an offer. Thus, in *Harvey V Facey*³² the plaintiff sent a telegraph to the defendant phrased as follow “will you sell us bumper hall pen? “Telegraph lowest price? The defendant replied by telegraph stating lowest cash price for bumper pen E900 the plaintiff in turn replied by in which they stated we agree to buy bumper pen for E900 asked for by you. The defendant did not reply to this last telegraph. It was held that no contract has been concluded between the parties for the sale of bumper hall pen. The first telegraph is as a mere enquiry in which the plaintiff simply sought to ascertain whether or not the defendant was willing to sell and if so at what price? The defendant offer was not an offer to sell the

²⁵ (2022) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1811) 209

²⁶ *Sagay* (n 3)

²⁷ (1993) NWLR 305 PG 320

²⁸ (1997) 7 NWLR 512 PAGE 204

²⁹ *Ibid*

³⁰ (1893) 1QB 256

³¹ *Ibid*

³² (1893) AC552

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property but a precise answer to the question that has been asked of him. The mere statement of the lowest price at which he was prepared to sell did not constitute an implied offer to sell at that price to the person making the inquiry.

The final telegraph sent by the plaintiff was therefore an offer not an acceptance and not having been accepted by the defendant could not give rise to a contract between the parties.

An offer and acceptance can be made expressly or by conduct implied. For example, a bus stopping at bus stop implies that the owner of the bus is making an offer to a person waiting at the bus stop. If that person enters the bus, he accepts the offer by his conduct. By the conduct of the bus owner the latter implies that he will carry the passenger safely to his destination and the latter also implies that he will pay the fare such contracts which come into existence by the conduct of the Parties are numerous and as ever increasing daily with advancing technology and mechanization. Money put into automated machines in return for a receipt or ticket and fees paid at toll gates are common Nigeria examples. The test of the existence of a contract in such cases is an objective one. In other words, it is not the subjective intention of the parties but what a reasonable person will infer from their conduct that the court uphold. This, in *Major Oni V. Communication Associates*,³³ the plaintiff made an offer to let his flats to the defendants; the latter modified the terms of the offer by including the installation of air-conditions. The plaintiff immediately installed the air-conditioners. It was held that this brought a contract into existence between the two parties. Although it was not explicitly stated in the judgement, it is clear that by installing the air conditioners the plaintiff had accepted the defendant's counter offer by conduct. The court did not consider the subjective intentions of the parties but what a reasonable person would infer from the conduct of the parties.

Similarly, in *Alfrotrin V. Attorney General of the Federation*.³⁴ The federal government of Nigeria ordered cement through a foreign company called gift investment. The latter chartered a ship belonging to the appellant to bring the cement from Barcelona, in Spain to Lagos. When the ship arrived, it was held up for many days because of congestion at Lagos ports and could not discharge its cargo of cement. Even though the federal government had no contractual relationships with the appellant which was operating under its agreement with Gilt Investment, out of its anxiety to home the cement discharged the federal government directed the appellant to move its ship to Tema in Ghana to discharge the cement. Then subsequently the appellant brought an action against the federal government for the recovery of demurrage the latter denied liability on the ground that there was no privity of contract between them and the appellant. It was held by the supreme court that there was a fresh contract between the federal government and the appellant. According to the Court, the request by the Federal Government that the appellant's ship should dwell to Tema was an offer which the appellant accepted by its conduct in actually ordering the ship to move to Tema in response to the government's request. Thus, it was held in these words;

The performance of a condition is sufficient acceptance without the notification of it under circumstances where an offeror in his offer impliedly indicates that he does not require the notification of the acceptance of the offer.³⁵

It is interesting that the supreme court went on to state that the contract lacked precise or asserted terms and conditions and that it was therefore not legally or enforceable at law that was a very roundabout way of stating that there was no contract between the federal government and the appellant. This is course does not affect the basic principle the court was following namely, that a valid acceptance can be made by conduct even in the absence of words or writing.³⁶

3.0 INVITATION TO TREAT DIFFERENT FROM OFFER

For an offer to be capable of acceptance; it must be definitely clear and final. If it is merely a preliminary move in negotiations which may lead to a contract, it is not an offer but an invitation to treat. It is therefore important to distinguish between an offer and an invitation to treat which is basically a move in negotiations which may lead to a contract. The offeror must not merely have been feeling his way towards an agreement, not "Merely initiating negotiations from which an agreement might or might not in time result" As Bowen, L. J stated in *Carlill V. Carbolic Smoke Co.*³⁷ A person making an offer becomes "liable to anyone who, before it is retracted, performs the conditions whereas by contrast, in invitations to treat" You (the offeror) offer to negotiate, or you issue advertisements that you have to sell, or houses to let, in which cases there is no offer to be bound by any contract. Such advertisements are offers to negotiate – offers to receive offers, etc.

On Distinction between offer and invitation to treat, the Supreme Court in *Oloja v. Gov., Benue State*³⁸ got the following to say;

³³ (Unreported) High Court of Lagos, Lamja, J. Suit No LD/625/71 Delivered on January 8, 1973 case book pg.1

³⁴ (1996) 9 NWLR (Pt. 475) 634

³⁵ *Ibid*

³⁶ Sagay (n3)

³⁷ (n 26)

³⁸ (2022) 3 NWLR (Pt. 1816) 1

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An offer must be distinguished from an invitation to treat. An invitation to treat is the first step in negotiations between the parties to a contract. It may or may not lead to a definite offer being made by one of the parties to the negotiation. An invitation to treat is not an offer that can be accepted to lead to an agreement or contract. An invitation to treat is not an offer capable of acceptance that will result in a contract with a legal relationship between the parties. It is merely a communication by which a party is invited to make an offer. Thus, it is different from an offer mainly on the ground that it is not made with the intention that it will create a binding relationship as soon as the person to whom it is addressed responds to the invitation.

Situations that Invitation to treat exist include Auction, Display of goods, Mere statement of price, Advertisement, tender etc.

4.0 TERMINATION OF AN OFFER IN CONTRACT LAW

In contract law, the termination of an offer signifies the end of an offer's availability for acceptance, preventing the formation of a binding agreement. This can occur through various mechanisms. This include; revocation, where the offeror withdraws the offer before acceptance, is effective upon communication to the offeree, as established in the English case of *Dickinson v Dodds*.³⁹ Similarly, rejection by the offeree, either expressly or through a counter-offer (which itself proposes new terms), terminates the original offer. The principle from *Hyde v Wrench*⁴⁰ in England, where a counter-offer for a lower price ended the initial offer, is mirrored in Nigerian law, as seen in cases like *Olaopa v. Obafemi Awolowo University*.⁴¹ An offer can also lapse due to time, expiring if not accepted within a stipulated period, or if none is specified, within a reasonable timeframe, as illustrated by *Ramsgate Victoria Hotel v Montefiore*.⁴² Furthermore, the death or incapacity of either party generally terminates the offer, especially for personal service contracts. Finally, the failure of a condition upon which the offer was made, such as a property remaining in good condition, as in *Financings Ltd v Stimson*,⁴³ will also lead to its termination. Nigerian contract law largely adheres to these common law principles, emphasizing that an offer must be "live" and open for acceptance to form a valid contract. For this study, revocation of offer will be considered in extenso.

Revocation of Offer

A revocation may be regarded as an act of the offeror, prior to the moment of acceptance. It shows a present intention to react to the offer. *Donovan, L.J; in Financings Ltd. V Stimson*⁴⁴ has put it very simply in the following words: "it is conceded and I think rightly so that if an offeror makes it clear that he does not want to go on with the transaction, it is properly treated as a revocation of his offer".

Williston Puts it this way:

"Any statement which clearly implies unwillingness to contract according to the terms of the offer is sufficient though the word "revoke" is not used. ⁴⁵ In *Payne V. Cave*⁴⁶ revocation is possible and effective any time before acceptance: up to this moment ex hypothesis; no legal obligation exists. Nor, as the law itself is ready to keep the offer open for a given period such an intimation is but a parcel of the original offer, which must stand or fall as a whole. The offeror may of course, bind himself by a separate and specific contract to keep the offer open; but the offeree, if such is his allegation, "Must provide all the elements of the valid contract, including assent and consideration.

The principle is not even affective by the fact that the offeror expressly stipulated a period of time within which the offeree should accept or reject the offer. Thus, in *Routledge's V. Grant*⁴⁷ Grant offered which the latter was expected to give a definite answer. Grant withdrew his offer before the end of the 6 weeks. It was held that the defendant was entitled to retract his offer even within 6 weeks if the offer had not yet been accepted. The plaintiff could only have held the defendant to his offer throughout the period he had brought the option by a separate and binding contract.

It is possible for the offeror to withdraw an offer at any time before the offer is accepted, his basic rules allow the offeror to withdraw but his revocation can only occur if the offer has not already been accepted. Once acceptance occurs, the contract is formed and revocation is not possible.⁴⁸ The offeror is stipulated period only if the offeree binds the offeror to his promise by furnishing, this was the decision of the court in the case of *Montfort V. Scott*.⁴⁹

³⁹ (1876) 2 Ch D 463

⁴⁰ (1893) AC552

⁴¹ (1997) 7 NWLR 512 PAGE 204

⁴² (1865-66) LR 1 Ex 109.

⁴³ (1962) 1. W. L.R. 1184

⁴⁴ (1962) 1. W. L.R. 1184

⁴⁵ Williston on Contracts. (3rd ed) vol. 1s.55 1961

⁴⁶ (1789) 3 term Rep 148

⁴⁷ (1828) 4 Bing 653; 130 ER 920

⁴⁸ Turner (n 2)

⁴⁹ (1973) 1 All E.R 198. C.A

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Unilateral offer cannot be withdrawn while the offeree is performing

There is one major example where the basic rule allowing revocation of an offer prior to acceptance will not apply. This is the so-called 'Unilateral contract'. Thus, wherever a continuing act amounts to the acceptance then the offeror is unable to withdraw the offer until such time as either. Thus, in a unilateral contract the offeree actually accepts the offer by performing his side of the bargain.⁵⁰

Principles in Unilateral Contract

- a. The ordinary rule of revocation can apply as the offeror can revoke his offer before acceptance and completion of the promised act.⁵¹ The rationale behind this rule is that before the completion of the promised act, there can be a valid revocation.
- b. There is the view that once performance has begun, there is valid acceptance of the offer that partial performance has taken place and so an offeror can revoke this usually called the Pollock view this is the view suggested by Sir Frederick Pollock in England.⁵²
- c. American view: the American suggestion is to the effect that there can be said to be a contract to pay on completion or the complete performance of the entire act. An implied or collateral contract which consists of an offer not to revoke before completion which lightens to a valid contract when performance has begun thus, if an offeror revokes, he may be sued on his second promise.
- d. Quantum Meruit: the view is to the effect that where the offeror revokes after performance has started, he is obliged to compensate the offeree for his trouble. A quantum meruit doctrine refers to recovery of compensation for the work done or expense involved or inconveniences associated with the performance of the uncompleted act this was conveyed in the case of *Luxox V. Cooper*.⁵³
- e. Irrevocable offer: option to renew here, where there is an express agreement in a unilateral contract which makes an offer irrevocable upon certain terms, the offeree cannot revoke upon performance of the term.
- f. Fusion of Pollock's and American view: this is the fusion of Pollock. It was advanced in English case of *Dualia V. four Mill bank nominees*.⁵⁴ Thus, the offeree or required to fully perform the contract which has been entered into and there is an implied obligation on the part of the offeror not to prevent the performances and so he cannot revoke his offer.

The offeror must communicate the withdrawal of the offer to the offeree

Communication is a critical factor throughout the whole process of offer and acceptance, for the reason already stated, while the offeror is entitled to withdraw the offer before acceptance of it, the fact of this withdrawal must be communicated to the offeree who otherwise would be unfairly treated any withdrawal of the offer that is not communicated is inevitably invalid. It is vital that notice of revocation should reach the offeree for otherwise he is entitled to treat the offer as continuing and capable of acceptance. Moreover, a revocation sent by post, unlike an acceptance, is not effective until it reaches the offeree, this means that an acceptance posted after a revocation has been posted, but not yet received, will be valid to create a binding contract. For instance, in *Bryne V. Van Tienhoven*⁵⁵ an offer to sell some goods was posted on October, this letter was received and a telegram of acceptance was dispatched on 11 October meanwhile on 8 October, the offeror posted a withdrawal of his offer, but this did not reach the offeree until 20 October. It was held that the dispatch of the telegram of acceptance collected the contract despite the fact that at that time a revocation was on its way. The case is a striking illustration of the objective approach of the law of contract, for in actual fact there was no moment of time at which both parties agreed on the making of the contract in the question. In *Re Zone Company Ltd.*⁵⁶ The applicant on the 23rd of May, 1962, applied for allocation of 200 shares from the respondent company and made a deposit of E500 on the 6th August 1962, the respondent received a letter from the applicant representing his offer and demand for the repayment of the deposits paid. The respondent replied that same day promising to communicate with the applicant as soon as the decision on his request. On the 17th August, 1962, the respondent company wrote a letter to the applicant informing him. The applicant brought an application for the rectification of the respondent company's register as a shareholder of the company. It was held by the court that the applicant had already withdrawn his offer, a fact which was known to the respondent company and therefore no contract as any allotment after the withdrawal was invalid.

⁵⁰ *Eyiboh v. Mujaddadi* (2022) 7 NWLR (Pt. 1830) 381

⁵¹ *Amana Suits Hotels Ltd. v. P.D.P.* (2007) 6 NWLR (Pt. 1031) 453

⁵² Pollock (n14) pg 19

⁵³ (1941) A C 108, see also *Errington V. Errington & words* (1952) 1 All E.R 149

⁵⁴ *U.D.T.V Eagle Aircrafts* (1968) 1 WLR. 74

⁵⁵ [1978] Ch 231

⁵⁶ (1880) 5 CpD 544, *Henthorn V. Eraser* (1887) 2 ch.27

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5.0 THE DILEMMA OF THE THIRD-PARTY INFORMATION ON REVOCATION

Due to business and commercial reasons, an offeror by law can withdraw his offer of a contract at any time before acceptance however we must be quick to state apposite among other things that the intention of the offeror on the revocation of his offer must be communicated to the offeree. In other words, if he relies on revocation, he must prove not only that he has done some act which manifests his intention but that the offeree has knowledge of this act.

One of the principles governing revocation is that whether by express words or by implication of conduct showing unambiguous present intention to revoke the revocation in order to be effective must be communicated to the offeree. It follows therefore that a unilateral change of mind by the offeror uncommunicated to the offeree is not enough.

This strict rule is adhered to in order to safeguard business interest if the notice of revocation is given orally by the offeror the communication is effected when the offeree hears of it. The same rule applies to the revocation made over the telephone. Thus, merely posting a letter of revocation the intention to withdraw the offer has not been communicated to the offeree; the revocation is only operative from the moment the letter of revocation is received by the offeree and it does not make any difference whether he reads it or not.

For the same reason if the letter of revocation was destroyed or lost in the post the attempted revocation is ineffective.⁵⁷

It is pertinent to draw to mind again the very fact that the information on the revocation of an offer need not be communicated to the offeree by the offeree himself but can be done also by a third party. However, the court gave a caveat (proviso) that this third party (one earlier defined as not being a party to the contract) must be a reliable source of information to both parties one who they could also rely on for a reliable information.⁵⁸

The dilemma of a third-party information on revocation can be seen from both ends i.e. the dilemma on the part of the offeree) as such all that can be said is a question of fact and circumstance in each situation.

We shall consider these dilemmas on revocation caused by a third party in two dimensions or categories;

- (i) The dilemma posed on the offeror by a third-party's information on his revocation
- (ii) The dilemma posed on the offeree by a third party's information on revocation.

5.1 PART 1: Dilemma of third party's information on revocation pose on the offeror.

The offeror is obliged by law to communicate his intention on revocation to the offeree at any time he so wishes to do so; however, this must be done before an acceptance is given to the offer. The complexity of the rule of revocation creates some impending problems which could be best considered as a dilemma as earlier stated while communicating an offer. The complexity of the rule of revocation creates some impending problems which could be best considered as dilemma as earlier stated while communication of an offer may easily be done by a mere post of a letter as was held in the case of *Adams V. Lindsell*.⁵⁹ where the defendant who were wool merchants wrote a letter to the plaintiff offering to sell a quantity of wool to the plaintiff. The letter of offer was signed 2nd September 1817 but it was misdirected and only arrived on 5th September that same evening on the 5th the plaintiff who were manufacturer of wool posted a letter accepting the offer on the 5th of September 1817. If the letter of the offer had not been misdirected, a reply should have been received by the 7th of September. On the 8th of September when no reply came the defendant sold the wool to another party. On 9th September they received the acceptance letter. The plaintiffs brought this action for conversion. The issue before the court was at what point was the acceptance made? There were no precedent cases on that and the King's bench posed three academic questions.

1. Could it be at the point of postage?
2. Could it be at the point of delivery of the letter?
3. Could it be at the point the offeror received notice of the acceptance?

The adoption of the first question by the king's bench has led to this strict law that even if the letter of acceptance gets missing in the case of postage, the contract is still valid.⁶⁰

The reverse of what is obtainable in communication of acceptance is found in the revocation, as observed above, a mere postage of letter confirms the offer but revocation demands that the letter or the information must reach the offeree. In *Stephen M. Weld and Co. V. Victory Mfg./Co.*⁶¹ The offeree received a message cancelling the order just twenty-five minutes after it wired its acceptance. The court held that "when the plaintiff on September 20 filed with the telegraph company at 10:15 am, the telegram accepting the offer, the contract was complete".

It is instructive to know that a third party can also communicate the information on revocation to the offeree. Practically, the post office can also be seen as a third party and it is in these situations that the dilemma lies.

⁵⁷ *Stevenson V. Maclean* (1880) 5 Q.B.D.346, see also O. Achike, Nigeria law of contract 1981

⁵⁸ *Dickinson. V. Dodds* (1876) 2 CLD 463

⁵⁹ (1818) 1 B & A 681

⁶⁰ *Household Fire Insurance Company V. Grant* (1879) 4 Exchequer Division 216.

⁶¹ 172 Tenn. 241 S. W.2 d851 (1951)

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This dilemma will be how to determine which means the offeree will be using to communicate his acceptance or the time which his letter on revocation could actually reach the offeree before he communicates his acceptance.

Succinctly, the offeror is in dilemma to determine whether the time he has sent his letter of revocation, the offeree has posted that of acceptance or not? He is also in a dilemma to determine who and what means could be reliable to communicate his intention (reliable in the sight of a reasonable man).

5.2 PART II: The Dilemma of Third-Party Information on Revocation Pose on the Offeree

In reiteration, the law demands that the offeror's information on revocation must be communicated to the offeree before he (offeree) makes his final and unqualified acceptance. However, there are times or circumstances where the information on revocation is usually not expressed by the offeror but impliedly communicated through a third party. An interesting fact situation was presented in the case of Hoover Motor Express Co. v. Clements Paper Co.⁶² Where the plaintiff had received a written offer from the defendant concerning the purchase of real estate.

No consideration was given for the offer. During a telephone conversation with the plaintiffs' partners expressed doubt whether they would go through with the proposal and stated that they had other plans in mind and would let the plaintiff. Offeree knows. The supreme court of Tennessee, held that the statement uttered by the offeror amounted to a withdrawal of offer.⁶³

In fact, it has been held by our courts that the offeree loses his power of acceptance if he learns by any way that the offer has been revoked, if he has reason to know that it does stand anymore or even if he has doubt and a reasonable person in his place would investigate whether the offer is still effective. The standard of a reasonable man is imposed on the offeree, and if it appears from the circumstance of the case that it is unreasonable to believe that the offer remains valid, the offeree cannot accept it any longer.⁶⁴

This dilemma is the problem of determining the reliability of the information reaching him on the offerors change of mind. He is certainly perplexed to accept indirect information or not? And even if he would accept the information, how can he determine if the information is truly from a reliable source, considering the fact that some are just rumours.

6.0 RESOLUTION OF THE DILEMMA

6.1 Part I

In order to resolve his dilemma, the offeror should find a reliable means of communicating his intention on revocation. He can use modern means of communication like text messages, phone call, WhatsApp etc. and he should always work with time to ensure that his revocation reaches the offeree before the latter communicates his acceptance. He should use a reliable third party who can be relied on.

6.2 Part II

In resolving the dilemma posed on the offeree by a third party's information on revocation, it is instructive to note that the position of this paper is that the offeree must contact the offeror to check the veracity of such information. In clear terms, the offeree after he must have sieved from the rumour some elements of reality that a reasonable man could accept but still doubts, he should contact the offeror to confirm the information.

7.0 CONCLUSION

Revocation of contractual offers can be done at any point before an acceptance is given by the offeree. However, the strict rule has always been that the intention of revocation of an offer by the offeror must be communicated to the offeree. It is not enough for him to withdraw his offer; he must make his intention known to the offeree. It must be instructive to also add that, he can do this by himself (expressly) or through a third party. The question again will be who is qualified to be a third party?

The case of Dickinson v. Dodds⁶⁵. The Court held that once a person to whom an offer to sell property is made, knows the property has been sold to someone else. It is too late to accept the offer. The plaintiff knew that Dodds was no longer minded to sell to him as plainly and clearly as if Dodds had told him in so many words " I withdraw the offer." This was held because Berry, a third party, had communicated the message to him although in a rumour, which indeed could constitute a dilemma, he would have to confirm the veracity from the offeror. The Court did not fail to point out that it is an objective test (can the information be regarded as being reliable in the sight of a reasonable man?) Hence, the offeree is not bound to always open his eyes to catch the gossip or rumour. On

⁶² Cited in W. J. Wagner, Some Problems of Revocation and Termination of Offers: Necessity of Communication-Time of Revocation-Death, (1963) 38 *Notre Dame Law Review*, 138 <<https://scholarship.law.nd.edu/ndlr/vol38/iss2/2>> accessed 20th June 2025.

⁶³ *Ibid*

⁶⁴ See the case of Byrne V. Van Tienhoven.

⁶⁵ (1876) 2 Ch D 463

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the part of the offeror, he has to determine whether the message about his revocation has been communicated or reached the offeree before the former post his acceptance. The study looked at the surrounding issues around revocation of an offer and the dilemma it could pose on the offeror and the offeree if the information on it is done by a third party. Using the cases of *Byrne v. Van Tienhoven* and *Dickinson v. Dodds*, for both the offeror and offeree this dilemma is observed and treated above with resolutions.

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